

1 Interpreting Intrusions - The Role of 2 Explainability in AI-Based Intrusion 3 Detection Systems

4 Marek Pawlicki^{1,2}, Aleksandra Pawlicka^{1,3}, Młcisław Śrutek², Rafał Kozik^{1,2},
5 and Michał Choraś^{1,2}

6 ¹ITTI Sp. z o.o., Poznań, Poland

7 ²Bydgoszcz University of Science and Technology, Bydgoszcz, Poland

8 ³University of Warsaw, Warsaw, Poland

9 ABSTRACT

Machine learning has become a key component of the effective detection of network intrusions. Yet, it comes with the lack of transparency - an issue which can be mitigated with the employment of explainable AI techniques. In this paper, the crucial role of explainability in intrusion detection is discussed, along with its benefits and drawbacks, followed by presenting and comparing the results of four main explainability techniques applied to an intrusion detection system.

Keywords: explainable AI; intrusion detection; machine learning

10 1 INTRODUCTION, MOTIVATION AND RATIONALE

11 In today's interconnected world, heavily relying on the Internet and related services, and threatened by a
12 wide variety of cyberattacks, intrusion detection systems (IDS), which provide real-time monitoring and
13 are capable of uncovering any suspicious activity, have become an inseparable component of the network
14 security paradigm. Yet, modern networks are becoming progressively more complex, and the sophistication
15 of cyberattacks constantly rises. As a result, it has been increasingly more difficult for IDSs to detect and
16 classify intrusions in an accurate manner Pawlicki et al. (2022).

17 One way to tackle this problem of IDSs has is with the use of machine learning (ML) algorithms;
18 they have shown promising results in improving detection accuracy. Still, these complex algorithms tend
19 to be opaque, i.e., they work in a black-box manner. This means that human operators are unable to
20 understand how a particular decision was made, and why Yan et al. (2022). In a situation where it is
21 impossible to achieve transparency of the decision-making process, concerns are raised about the reliability
22 and trustworthiness of the models. This issue becomes all the more important in high-stakes domains, such
23 as healthcare, autonomous vehicles, finances, and, as in the case of this work, cybersecurity Capuano et al.
24 (2022)Nwakanma et al. (2023).

25 This lack of transparency gave rise to the postulate of making AI explainable; thus, the concept
26 of explainable AI (xAI) was introduced. Explainability refers to the humans' ability to understand and
27 interpret the decision-making process of ML algorithms. In the context of intrusion detection, explainability
28 may help identify the critical features of the data that contribute to a particular decision, making it easier
29 for human analysts to understand the nature of the threat and develop effective countermeasures. On
30 top of that, explainability can lead to identifying biases and errors in the ML models, resulting in their
31 performance getting improved Sharma et al. (2022).

32 This paper highlights the pivotal role of explainability in intrusion detection systems and discusses the
33 challenges and opportunities associated with the use of xAI techniques in this domain. The most relevant
34 xAI methods are briefly presented. Then, the results of an experiment are shown, in which a number of
35 state-of-the-art explainability techniques are employed in an intrusion detection system. The results are
36 juxtaposed, with the conclusions drawn thereafter.

37 2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

38 xAI techniques are being increasingly used in intrusion detection. These techniques offer insights into the
39 decision-making processes of ML algorithms, facilitating human understanding of the rationale behind a
40 particular decision.

2.1 Advantages and Limitations of xAI Techniques

There are several advantages to intrusion detection that the application of xAI techniques brings about. First of all, the xAI techniques can shed light on the decision-making process of ML models. Thanks to this, it becomes easier for human analysts to understand how and why a particular decision was made. This further leads to improved trust in the ML models; consequently, their adoption in real-world settings could increase as a result Molnar (2022). Additionally, xAI techniques can help to identify biases and errors in the ML models, the correction of which will positively influence their performance Doshi-Velez and Kim (2017).

It has also been argued that xAI techniques facilitate the development of more effective and efficient countermeasures against potential threats by providing insight into the factors that contribute to a particular decision. xAI techniques may help to find and pinpoint the critical aspects of the data that require attention when investigating potential threats. This can lead to more targeted and precise investigations, ultimately saving time and resources Gunning et al. (2019).

The application of xAI techniques has the potential to facilitate collaboration between human analysts and ML models. Specifically, xAI techniques provide interpretable representations of the decision-making process, which enables human analysts to validate the decisions made by ML models as well as provide feedback for improvement. This results in a more effective partnership between human analysts and ML models, ultimately improving the overall performance of the intrusion detection system Gunning et al. (2019).

Yet, xAI techniques are not free of potential shortcomings. One such drawback is the trade-off between interpretability and accuracy. This means that making models interpretable in order to understand the decision-making process may impede their level of accuracy, in comparison with the more complex, black-box models Doshi-Velez and Kim (2017).

Despite these drawbacks, xAI techniques have shown promise in improving the transparency and interpretability of ML models in intrusion detection. In the context of intrusion detection, xAI techniques can provide insights into the decision-making process, identify biases and errors, and facilitate collaboration between human analysts and ML models Molnar (2022).

There are a number of xAI techniques which could be employed in intrusion detection; some of the most prominent ones have been discussed below.

2.2 Overview of xAI Techniques applicable in Intrusion Detection

Model-agnostic techniques provide local explanations for individual predictions. As the name suggests, they can be applied to any ML model. In the context of intrusion detection, the methods of this kind allow security analysts to better understand how a particular prediction was made. This is particularly valuable when the models are complex, making it fairly possible for humans to interpret. Some of the most recognizable techniques of this kind are LIME, SHAP; DiCE and ProtoDash.

LIME (Local Interpretable Model-Agnostic Explanations) is a technique that generates locally faithful explanations for individual predictions by fitting an interpretable model to the neighbourhood of the input data, thus providing an insight into a complex model by generating a much simpler, locally interpretable linear model Ribeiro et al. (2016).

SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) is a technique that assigns a value to each input feature based on its contribution to the model's prediction, leveraging cooperative game theory. The method exploits Shapley values, which are used to fairly allocate the payoff among players in a coalition, treating features as players and the model output as payoff Lundberg and Lee (2017).

DiCE (Diverse Counterfactual Explanations) provides counterfactual explanations - informative samples which answer the question 'What would it take to change the label on this sample?'. DiCE synthesises those data points by perturbing features of a sample until the label flips, essentially presenting a 'what-if' scenario. The particular way of finding the data points is an optimisation problem similar to the generation of adversarial attacks, perturbing the features which maximise the effect on the label and minimise the amount of necessary perturbation Mothilal et al. (2020). DiCE Counterfactuals are a valuable supplement to other xAI techniques.

ProtoDash allows to find 'Prototypical Samples' of a set of data, which, for a labelled dataset, can be used to gain insight into the characteristics of a subset, or a specific class of data, through its most representative samples. ProtoDash provides a concise representation of the given class. The samples are found by maximising similarity Gurumoorthy et al. (2019).

3 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND RESULTS

The experiment was carried out on an open, public cybersecurity benchmark, the CICIDS2018 subset of the Netflow Collection, which is a conversion of the CICIDS2018 Sharafaldin et al. (2018) dataset to the

98 Netflow format Sarhan et al. (2021). Before using the dataset, the duplicate values were dropped and the
99 categorical features were encoded via Frequency Encoding. The set was split into training and testing set
100 (80/20), stratifying the sets by the target label. The training set was balanced using random subsampling
101 on the majority (Benign) class to the number of the sum of samples of all the attack classes, achieving
102 1:1 ratio attack:benign. Before inputting to the neural network, the features are scaled using scikit-learn's
103 StandardScaler.

104 A neural network is trained on the training set, the hyperparameters are listed in Table 1. The
105 hyperparameters were chosen using the hyperband algorithm Li et al. (2017). The used framework is
106 TensorFlow Abadi et al. (2016). The model's performance is evaluated using a standard set of metrics,
107 contained in Table 2.

108 In addition to Accuracy, Precision and Recall, Hamming loss, Matthews Correlation Coefficient and
109 Balanced Accuracy are calculated to give a better overview of the model performance.

110 Hamming loss measures the number of mistakenly classified samples to the total number of samples,
111 estimated as the hamming distance between y_{true} and $y_{predicted}$. The measure ranges from 0 to 1, with
112 0 being the better classifier.

113 The Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC) takes into account all the elements of a confusion matrix:
114 true positive (TP), true negative (TN), false positive (FP), and false negative (FN), providing a balanced
115 assessment of classification. The score ranges from -1 to 1, with 0 being no better than random chance, 1
116 representing the perfect score, and -1 the opposite. The equation for MCC is given in Eq. (1).

$$MCC = \frac{(TP \times TN) - (FP \times FN)}{\sqrt{(TP + FP)(TP + FN)(TN + FP)(TN + FN)}} \quad (1)$$

117 Balanced Accuracy is a metric particularly useful in imbalanced datasets, it is the average of sensitivity
118 and specificity, as displayed in Eq. (2).

$$BACC = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{TP}{(TP + FN)} + \frac{TN}{(TN + FP)} \right) \quad (2)$$

119 With the detection model established and evaluated, the experiment proceeded with attempting to
120 gain insight into the decision making process of the classifier. To this end, the four xAI methods were
121 employed: SHAP, LIME, DiCE and ProtoDash. Following a scenario where a security operative needs to
122 justify a decisive action to ban or not to ban a user based on the detection result, the focus will be on local
123 explanations, which will, in principle, provide reasoning as to why the samples in question were classified
124 as an attack.

125 3.1 xAI Interpretation

126 An attack was randomly selected from the attack classes; the model predicted the sample to be a 'DOS-
127 Hulk' attack. The analysis begins with the SHAP summary plot, which showcases the feature importance
128 calculated for the entire test set, as seen in Fig. 1. The feature importance is sorted, and its contribution
129 to particular classes is depicted in colour. With the general overview of the behaviour of the model, the
130 SHAP force plot is used to understand the contributions of features to the particular classification of the
131 'DOS-Hulk' sample, as seen in Fig. 2. The force plot falls in line with the summary plot, with 'L7 Proto'
132 being the strongest feature, closely followed by 'TCP FLAG'. However, this explanation is contradicted by
133 the one coming from LIME in Fig. 3, where the local interpretable linear model considered 'Flow Duration'
134 and 'Out Packets' to be the two most contributive features. Following LIME, ProtoDash was used to gain
135 insight into the characteristics of the 'DoS-Hulk' class. In Table 3, three prototypical samples selected by
136 the algorithm are showcased, along with their feature values and the weight - the relevance of the sample
137 with respect to the representation of the explained instance class. The explained sample is given at the
138 bottom row of the table. Finally, DiCE is employed to find counterfactual samples, which are listed in Tab.
139 4, with the explained sample listed at the bottom of the table. The target label of the DiCE algorithm was
140 selected to be 'Benign', so the found counterfactuals answer the question 'What would have to change so
141 this sample is classified as Benign'. It is noteworthy that of the five proposed counterfactuals, three have a
142 very similar flow duration to the explained sample, which contradicts the immense importance attributed to
143 that value by the LIME algorithm.

144 4 CONCLUSIONS

145 While the field of explainability of AI is a hot research topic, with some methods gaining prominence in the
146 research environment, the experimental results in a real-world setting suggest that the available methods

Table 1. Hyperparameters of the Neural Network Model

Hyperparameter	Value
Optimizer	Adam
Learning Rate	0.0001
Hidden Layers	2
Units in Layer 1	360
Activation in Layer 1	ReLU
Units in Layer 2	360
Activation in Layer 2	ReLU
Output Activation	Softmax
Loss Function	Categorical Crossentropy
Batch Size	2
Epochs	50
Early Stopping Monitor	Loss
Early Stopping Patience	5

Results	Accuracy	BACC	MCC	Precision	Recall	Hamming Loss
	0.873	0.441	0.795	0.853	0.873	0.127

Table 2. Results of the classification model

Figure 1. SHAP: average impact on model output

Figure 2. SHAP: contributions of features to the classification for the specific 'DOS-Hulk' sample

Table 3. Protodash Prototypes selected by the algorithm for the sample given at the bottom of the table

	INB	OUTB	INP	OUTP	FLOW DUR.	L7	PROT	DST PORT	TCPFL	Weight	Label
0	172.0	2861.0	4.0	68.0	4294942.0	0	6	3389	219	0.981968	DoS attacks-Hulk
1	743.0	1269.0	6.0	6.0	4294905.0	92	6	22	219	0.009456	DoS attacks-Hulk
2	848.0	2264.0	11.0	10.0	4238765.0	83	6	63991	219	0.007987	DoS attacks-Hulk
	172	2821	4	9	4294949	0	6	3389	219	-	DoS attacks-Hulk

Table 4. Counterfactual Samples synthesized with DiCE

	INB	OUTB	INP	OUTP	FLOW DUR.	L7	PROT	DST PORT	TCPFL	Label
0	14496782.0	2103.0	13.0	9.0	3685515.2	0.0	6	3389	219	Benign
1	4609669.5	2103.0	13.0	9.0	4291385.0	0.0	58	3389	219	Benign
2	1991.0	2103.0	36057.535	9.0	4291385.0	0.0	6	3389	219	Benign
3	1991.0	70182360.0	13.0	9.0	3222583.0	0.0	6	3389	219	Benign
4	1991.0	2103.0	13.0	9.0	4291385.0	0.0	6	3389	4	Benign
Samp.	172	2821	4	9	4294949	0	6	3389	219	DoS attacks-Hulk

Figure 3. LIME for a sample from the DOS-Hulk class

147 are not capable of producing coherent, logical and consistent results. On top of that, no set methodology to
 148 evaluate the accuracy and correctness of the provided explanations is available, nor is a formal methodology
 149 to compare the obtained explanations. While the employed techniques provide some sort of insight into the
 150 behaviour of the model, experimental results suggest that even though the importance of certain features to
 151 the classification is provided, it is relatively easy to produce samples with different labels by perturbing less
 152 relevant features. The clear future direction of this field is to establish a formal methodology to compare
 153 the xAI methods and to evaluate their quality.

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157 CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

158 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

159 REFERENCES

- 160 Abadi, M., Barham, P., Chen, J., Chen, Z., Davis, A., Dean, J., Devin, M., Ghemawat, S., Irving, G., Isard,
 161 M., et al. (2016). Tensorflow: A system for large-scale machine learning. In *12th {USENIX} Symposium
 162 on Operating Systems Design and Implementation ({OSDI} 16)*, pages 265–283.
- 163 Capuano, N., Fenza, G., Loia, V., and Stanzione, C. (2022). Explainable artificial intelligence in cybersecurity: A survey. *IEEE Access*, 10:93575–93600.
- 164 Doshi-Velez, F. and Kim, B. (2017). Towards A Rigorous Science of Interpretable Machine Learning.
- 165 Gunning, D., Stefik, M., Choi, J., Miller, T., Stumpf, S., and Yang, G.-Z. (2019). XAI—Explainable
 166 artificial intelligence. *Science Robotics*, 4(37).
- 167 Gurumoorthy, K. S., Dhurandhar, A., Cecchi, G., and Aggarwal, C. (2019). Efficient data representation by
 168 selecting prototypes with importance weights. In *2019 IEEE International Conference on Data Mining
 169 (ICDM)*, pages 260–269. IEEE.
- 170 Li, L., Jamieson, K., DeSalvo, G., Rostamizadeh, A., and Talwalkar, A. (2017). Hyperband: A novel
 171 bandit-based approach to hyperparameter optimization. *The Journal of Machine Learning Research*,
 172 18(1):6765–6816.
- 173 Lundberg, S. M. and Lee, S.-I. (2017). A Unified Approach to Interpreting Model Predictions. In Guyon,
 174 I., Luxburg, U. V., Bengio, S., Wallach, H., Fergus, R., Vishwanathan, S., and Garnett, R., editors,
 175 *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, volume 30. Curran Associates, Inc.
- 176 Molnar, C. (2022). *Interpretable Machine Learning (Second Edition) A Guide for Making Black Box
 177 Models Explainable*. Leanpub.
- 178 Mothilal, R. K., Sharma, A., and Tan, C. (2020). Explaining machine learning classifiers through diverse
 179 counterfactual explanations. In *Proceedings of the 2020 Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and
 180 Transparency*, pages 607–617.

- 182 Nwakanma, C. I., Ahakonye, L. A. C., Njoku, J. N., Odirichukwu, J. C., Okolie, S. A., Uzondu, C.,
183 Ndubuisi Nweke, C. C., and Kim, D.-S. (2023). Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) for Intrusion
184 Detection and Mitigation in Intelligent Connected Vehicles: A Review. *Applied Sciences*, 13(3):1252.
- 185 Pawlicki, M., Kozik, R., and Choraś, M. (2022). A survey on neural networks for (cyber-) security and
186 (cyber-) security of neural networks. *Neurocomputing*, 500:1075–1087.
- 187 Ribeiro, M., Singh, S., and Guestrin, C. (2016). Why Should I Trust You?: Explaining the Predictions of
188 Any Classifier. In *2016 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational
189 Linguistics: Demonstrations*, San Diego.
- 190 Sarhan, M., Layeghy, S., Moustafa, N., and Portmann, M. (2021). Netflow datasets for machine learning-
191 based network intrusion detection systems. In *Big Data Technologies and Applications: 10th EAI
192 International Conference, BDTA 2020, and 13th EAI International Conference on Wireless Internet,
193 WiCON 2020, Virtual Event, December 11, 2020, Proceedings 10*, pages 117–135. Springer.
- 194 Sharafaldin, I., Lashkari, A. H., and Ghorbani, A. A. (2018). Toward generating a new intrusion detection
195 dataset and intrusion traffic characterization. *ICISSp*, 1:108–116.
- 196 Sharma, D. K., Mishra, J., Singh, A., Govil, R., Srivastava, G., and Lin, J. C.-W. (2022). Explainable
197 Artificial Intelligence for Cybersecurity. *Computers and Electrical Engineering*, 103:108356.
- 198 Yan, F., Wen, S., Nepal, S., Paris, C., and Xiang, Y. (2022). Explainable machine learning in cybersecurity:
199 A survey. *International Journal of Intelligent Systems*, 37(12):12305–12334.

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